

GRØN DYST Abstract Guidelines for Authors

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ABSTRACT

The transport sector is one of the sectors that provide the greatest impact on the environment, air and noise pollution in cities and provide a large CO₂ emissions. Therefore it is important with a “sustainable development”, which is a development that simultaneously takes into account the environmental, social and economic dimensions of society.

Figure 1 - The 3 dimensions of sustainability

A solution will be a Smart City which integrates state of the art green technologies to create a city that is both sustainable and can deliver high living standards.

The Smart City can be defined as a city which makes it surplus into resources through its use of information and communication technologies combined with sustainable and environmentally friendly multiple solutions.

In this project we will introduce a new ITS system that can positively contribute to increase mobility and thus to sustainable development.

The project will examine the possibility of a new ITS (Intelligent Transport System) in Copenhagen and how such a system can contribute to sustainability for the transport sector in the region. The concept will focus on environmental, social and economic dimensions of sustainability.

- The new system must reduce congestion in the city and thereby reduce greenhouse gases emitted by vehicles.
- The system will try to utilize the social link between people and perhaps use some form of shared vehicle concept.
- All expenses in implementing this ITS will be estimated and will be compared to the value of the benefits.